

ISic3484

I.Sicily inscription 3484

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

list

Material

limestone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

amphitheatre, Siracusa, in work of earth removal at southern side,
1916-1918

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 37628

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336191

1. [ὁ δεῖνα — —μέ]νεος vac.
2. [ὁ δεῖνα — —]μένεος
3. [ὁ δεῖνα Καλ]λίβιος
4. [— — — — —]εος
5. [— — — — —]
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645105

PHI 336191

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 68 no.60 fig.142

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